

What is a Blast? How to Design a Representative Pre-Clinical Model

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Abstract

Pre-clinical blast models vary widely in their design, using diverse subjects (animals and cells), mediums (air and water), and energy sources (wires, explosives, and gas) and levels (low to very high) to study and simulate blast exposure. While these models are often described as simulating “blast” exposure, variability exists in the resulting pressure time histories, including differences in peak pressure, duration, confinement, shock source, and the presence of a negative phase. These waveform characteristics significantly influence the overall exposure experienced during a blast, and potentially, injury outcomes. The objective of the paper is to define what physically constitutes a blast wave, distinguishing it from shock dominated pressure profiles that may result from non-explosive sources. Using this definition, existing pre-clinical blast models are evaluated with respect to their ability to reproduce blast waveforms. By analyzing these models, this paper identifies key limitations and provides guidance for designing representative pre-clinical exposure models that better reproduce blast wave characteristics. Improving blast waveform fidelity is important to improve the translation of pre-clinical experimental findings to clinical blast-induced injuries.

Introduction

Blast-induced traumatic brain injury (bTBI) has emerged as a significant concern in both military and civilian populations¹⁻³, with increasing attention on the underlying mechanisms, injury

thresholds, and long-term consequences of blast exposure⁴⁻⁷. Despite advancements in neurotrauma research, the complex nature of blast waves and their interaction with biological tissues presents challenges in accurately replicating blast conditions in laboratory settings. Pre-clinical models play an important role in explaining the pathophysiology of blast exposure; however, variability in design, methodology, and exposure parameters raises questions regarding their translational relevance to human injury^{6,8}.

Pre-clinical blast models utilize a range of biological subjects, including cell cultures^{6,9-11}, and small and large animals models¹²⁻¹⁷, to investigate the effects of blast exposure on neurological and systemic health. Additional studies have used instrumented synthetic human surrogates^{18,19} and human cadaveric tissue²⁰ to better approximate human biomechanical response. The medium through which blast waves propagate, whether air, water, or solid materials, significantly impacts wave transmission and injury mechanisms²¹⁻²³. Moreover, the energy sources used to generate blast waves, such as explosives^{12,17}, compressed gas^{18,24}, or wire-driven mechanisms^{25,26}, produce varying waveforms that differ in overpressure (the pressure above ambient atmospheric pressure), rate of rise, peak intensity, duration, confinement effects, and the presence of a negative phase^{18,27,28}. These parameters are critical in defining the severity of blast exposure and must be carefully controlled to ensure experimental outcomes reflect real-world conditions. Despite efforts to replicate operationally relevant blast environments, it remains unclear which physical parameters most strongly drive biological injury. The mechanisms by which cells detect and respond to blast-induced stress are not understood, and may differ across cell types, underscoring the need for continued research to link physical exposure characteristics with specific biological outcomes.

While incoming threats (such as IEDs or explosive ordnance) typically involve high-intensity, multi-directional blast waves²⁹⁻³¹, outgoing threats (such as weapons fire) generate lower-amplitude but are more likely to be repetitive overpressure exposures^{32,33,33,34}. Understanding the differences between incoming and outgoing blast threats is important for developing representative pre-clinical models. Military personnel may be exposed to blast waves from improvised explosive devices (IEDs)³⁵⁻³⁷, breaching operations^{29,32,38}, shoulder-fired weapons^{32,39}, and heavy artillery^{32,33}, each of which produces distinct overpressure profiles. The relevance of pre-clinical models to these scenarios is an essential consideration when designing experiments that aim to inform military safety guidelines and medical countermeasures.

Despite significant progress in experimental blast research, key limitations remain in current pre-clinical models, particularly in their ability to fully replicate human-relevant exposure conditions. Many models lack fidelity in wave propagation mechanics, head-neck biomechanics, and multi-system injury interactions, leading to potential discrepancies between animal studies and clinical observations. Furthermore, inconsistencies in blast model design, such as differences in shock tunnel geometries, exposure durations, and subject positioning, complicate cross-study comparisons and hinder the development of standardized injury thresholds^{8,27,28}.

The term “blast” is commonly used with experimental exposures without clear agreement on whether the resulting pressure time profiles represent a military blast exposure. Differences in magnitude, waveform shape, duration, impulse, decay rate, and negative phase development can alter mechanical loading, yet are not consistently accounted for when classifying or comparing pre-clinical models or compared to relevant clinical exposures.

The objective of this work is to define what constitutes a blast wave based on the underlying physics of explosive events and military exposure, and to use this definition to evaluate pre-clinical blast models reported in literature. By distinguishing blast waveforms from shock waves, this work identifies limitations in current experimental approaches and provides guidance on selecting or designing representative pre-clinical models that accurately reproduce blast relevant loading conditions. Addressing these challenges will be essential in improving understanding of blast-induced neurotrauma by improving cross study comparability and interpretation of biological outcomes.

Blast Exposure in Military Context:

Military personnel are frequently exposed to blast events in both combat and training environments^{40–46}. These exposures can be broadly categorized into two types: incoming threats, where the blast wave originates from an external explosive device such as an improvised explosive device (IED), and outgoing threats, where the shock is generated by the service member’s own weapon system or breaching operations^{47,48}. Each exposure type is associated with distinct pressure time profiles, reflecting differences in waveform shape, impulse, decay rate, and positive and negative phases. Incoming explosive threats may involve larger charge sizes and more fully developed blast waveforms while outgoing exposures may produce shorter duration, shock dominated or blast like profiles depending on weapon system, standoff distance, and confinement^{32,33,39}. Understanding these distinctions is crucial for accurately modeling blast exposure in pre-clinical research and developing effective protective strategies.

Figure 1: Incoming and outgoing blast threats with the wave expansion shown in red A: incoming from a missile B: outgoing from a shoulder fired weapon C: incoming from a mine blast under a vehicle D: outgoing from a breaching charge. Figures adapted from ^{21,49-51}

Incoming Blast Threats

Incoming threats primarily stem from explosive devices deployed by adversaries, including IEDs, landmines, artillery shells, and other munitions ⁵²⁻⁵⁵. Figure 1A shows an artillery shell as an example of an incoming blast, while Figure 1C shows an underbody blast from a buried explosive, such as a mine or IED. These detonations create high-intensity blast waves that propagate outward, exposing personnel to significant overpressure and potential secondary injuries from shrapnel or structural collapse ^{53,56}. One of the key factors influencing the severity of exposure is the distance between the detonation point and the individual. Blast overpressure decreases with increasing distance from the explosion due to spherical expansion; however, factors such as enclosed spaces, walls, and vehicles can alter the blast wave through reflections and constructive interference, amplifying local pressure conditions and extending the positive phase duration ⁵⁷⁻⁶¹. Military personnel in combat zones are often exposed to repeated blast events, which may have cumulative effects on the brain and other organs ^{43,62,63}.

Direct measurements of pressure waves from incoming threats are limited, due to the challenges of instrumenting detonations during combat. Consequently, most research focuses on IEDs in vehicles, where blast loading can be measured in controlled conditions ^{35,36,64}. Incoming threats often involve a substantial fragmentation hazard, with injury mechanisms arising from both overpressure and high-velocity debris. In laboratory and training environments, outgoing blast

exposures are more feasible to study because test conditions, geometry, and the number of exposures can be tightly controlled. Expanding experimental characterization of incoming pressure environments remains an important area for improving injury prediction and protective strategies. The prevalence of injuries resulting from incoming versus outgoing blast exposures is not well known. Incoming threats are usually isolated, high-magnitude events and may involve additional non-primary blast injury mechanisms, such as whole-body acceleration or displacement due to blast forces. Therefore, replicating all aspects in a pre-clinical laboratory setting can be difficult.

Outgoing Blast Threats

Unlike incoming threats, outgoing blast exposures result from the service member's own use of weapon systems or explosive charges. These exposures occur in multiple scenarios, including heavy weapons fire, shoulder-launched missile systems, artillery operations, and breaching procedures^{29,32,33,37,39,65,66}. One common source of outgoing blast exposure is the shock wave produced when a bullet or projectile exits the barrel of a firearm^{32,39,67}. The magnitude of the overpressure depends on the caliber of the weapon, the type of ammunition, and whether a suppressor or muzzle brake is used^{32,39}. Larger-caliber weapons, such as anti-materiel rifles or automatic grenade launchers shown in Figure 1B, generate significantly greater overpressure than small arms^{39,68}. The negative phase of the shock wave, the period following the initial overpressure where ambient pressure drops below atmospheric levels, also varies between weapons, with some systems producing a more pronounced and extended negative phase that may contribute to unique physiological effects. Breaching operations such as those in Figure 1D, involve the controlled use of explosives to force entry into buildings or vehicles, are another source of outgoing blast exposure^{29,30,32,38}. Breaching charges are often placed against doors, walls, or other barriers, creating a highly directional blast wave⁶⁹. The proximity of the breacher to the charge, as well as the level of confinement, determines the severity of exposure³⁹. In enclosed spaces, multiple wave reflections can significantly amplify pressure levels^{60,70,71}, increasing the risk of bTBI and other injuries. Outgoing blast exposure levels are easier to replicate in a pre-clinical setting than incoming threats because weapon system or breaching parameters and proximity to the event can be quantified as these exposures often occur in controlled training environments.

Figure 2 shows waveforms measured from operational shoulder fired military weapon systems. Despite belonging to a similar class of outgoing threats, these systems show differences in peak overpressure, waveform structure, impulse, and presence of a negative phase. The variability in waveform shape shows that peak pressure alone is insufficient to characterize blast exposure. These waveforms can help provide an empirical baseline for evaluating whether pre-clinical blast models reproduce operationally relevant blast conditions.

Figure 2: Waveforms from military weapon systems A: Carl Gustaf B: SMAW (shoulder launched multipurpose assault weapon)
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Blast Overpressure and Distance Scaling

The relationship between blast overpressure and distance from the detonation point follows a well-defined physical scaling law ^{72,73}. In an ideal free-field explosion, the peak overpressure decreases approximately according to an inverse cube root relationship with increasing distance. This cube root scaling arises from the three-dimensional nature of blast wave propagation, where the energy disperses over an expanding spherical wavefront ⁷². As a result, explosive events of different charge sizes can be scaled to produce the same peak overpressure but does not result in equivalent pressure time histories. Reducing charge size while decreasing distance inherently reduces the total energy available to drive gas expansion, leading to shorter positive phase durations, even when peak pressures are matched ⁷³. However, in real-world settings, additional factors such as ground reflections, atmospheric conditions, and structural confinement can modify this scaling behavior.

One of the challenges in pre-clinical blast research is replicating large-scale explosive events within the constraints of experimental testing. Small-scale models inherently generate shock waves with shorter durations and steeper pressure gradients than those encountered in battlefield scenarios ⁷³. To address this, researchers must use appropriate scaling methodologies to extrapolate experimental data to human-relevant conditions. Mass scaling, which adjusts exposure parameters based on body mass, provides a generalized approach but does not fully capture species-specific anatomical differences ⁷⁴. Brain scaling, which focuses on neural tissue mass and structure, offers a more refined framework for neurotrauma research but may overlook factors such as skull composition and intracranial biomechanics ^{74,75}. Head scaling models, such as Jean's scaling approach, consider head-specific parameters, including skull thickness and brain volume, making them particularly relevant for bTBI studies ⁷⁴⁻⁷⁶. Scaling approaches focused on the head or brain may not account for systemic contributions to injury.

Distinguishing Blast, Shock, and Noise Exposures in Pre-Clinical Blast Research

Understanding the distinction between blast exposure, shock exposure, and noise exposure is important for pre-clinical blast research, as different exposure conditions influence injury mechanisms and outcomes. While these terms are sometimes used interchangeably, they describe distinct physical phenomena with different implications for brain injury. This section defines the physical characteristics that distinguish a blast wave from other forms of overpressure loading, and uses these criteria to evaluate whether commonly used experimental models in literature reproduce blast relevant waveforms. Establishing the distinctions in these exposures provides a framework for designing pre-clinical models intended to replicate military relevant blast conditions.

Physics of Blast Events

Blast events are governed by fundamental physical principles that dictate the formation, propagation, and interaction of pressure waves with surrounding environments. An understanding of these mechanisms is essential for designing pre-clinical models that accurately replicate real-world blast exposure conditions. The three primary components of blast physics; detonation mechanisms, gas expansion dynamics, and blast wave propagation, each play a role in shaping the exposure profile and potential injury outcomes.

Shock Waves

A shock wave is a compression wave that propagates through a medium at a velocity exceeding the local speed of sound (343 m/s in air at sea level) ⁷⁷⁻⁸⁰. Shock waves are characterized by a sharp, nearly instantaneous rise in pressure, temperature, and density at the wave front, followed by a pressure decay ^{78,79,81}. Shock waves may be generated by explosive detonations, high speed impacts, supersonic projectiles, and rapidly driven compression systems such as shock tubes. The presence of a shock front alone does not define a blast exposure. Shock waves generated by non-explosive sources can have a rapid pressure rise but may differ from explosive blast waves in terms of decay rate, impulse, and the presence of a negative phase.

Detonation Mechanisms and Blast Wave Formation

A blast wave is a specific form of shock wave generated by the detonation of an energetic material that occupies a finite volume and undergoes rapid chemical transformation ²². Detonations involve rapid chemical reactions that convert solid or liquid explosives into high-pressure gaseous products forcing the surrounding medium outward at supersonic velocity ^{22,82} and generating a strong shock front that propagates faster than the speed of sound ⁸³⁻⁸⁶. As such, all blast waves are shock waves, but not all shock waves are blast waves.

The defining feature of a blast wave is not just the initial shock front, but the coupled pressure time history produced by explosive gas expansion. Following the initial shock, continued expansion of detonation gases produces a high pressure positive phase during which pressure decays as energy

is distributed into the surrounding medium ^{21,22}. As the gases expand, a low pressure region is created behind the positive phase. This under pressurized region draws surrounding medium back toward the source, producing the negative phase of the blast waveform.

Gas Expansion Dynamics

In open environments, blast waves dissipate relatively quickly due to free expansion and energy dispersion, producing the classic free-field pressure time profile ^{21,22}. However, ground reflections or the presence of obstacles can create complex wave interactions that alter the exposure pattern ^{60,71,87,88}. In contrast, confined environments significantly alter gas expansion dynamics. Waves in enclosed spaces undergo reflection, leading to increased pressures and prolonged exposure durations that differ from those observed in free-field detonations ^{60,71,89}. These effects are particularly relevant in military scenarios, where blast exposures often occur in enclosed or semi-enclosed environments such as armored vehicles, bunkers, and urban structures. When waves encounter rigid surfaces, reflection can result in localized pressure amplification ^{90,91}. In contrast, interactions with softer or impedance mismatched materials, including biological tissue, can lead to partial transmission and reflection of wave energy ⁹²⁻⁹⁴.

Blast Exposure, Shock Exposure, and Noise: Definitions and Key Distinctions

Blast and Shock Exposure

Within this framework, blast exposure refers specifically to events in which an explosive detonation generates a blast wave consisting of an initial shock front followed by a high pressure positive phase and a subsequent negative phase before returning to equilibrium ⁸¹. The defining characteristic of blast exposure is the explosive driven coupling of shock formation and gas expansion, which together help determine the impulse and rate of decay leading to the overall waveform shape. Shock exposure, by contrast, refers more broadly to any pressure wave traveling at a velocity exceeding the speed of sound in the given medium ⁸⁰.

Noise Exposure

Noise exposure represents a fundamentally different phenomenon, consisting of pressure fluctuations over a broad range of frequencies without a sudden, sustained rise in pressure ⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷. Noise exposure in military and industrial settings can still have physiological effects, particularly at high intensities, but it lacks the distinct overpressure profile of a shock or blast wave ⁹⁸⁻¹⁰⁰. The frequency content of an explosion-generated waveform is particularly relevant when assessing potential injuries, as low-frequency waves penetrate deeper into biological tissues ^{96,101,102}, while high-frequency components influence surface-level damage.

Implications for Pre-Clinical Blast Modeling

Shock tunnels and advanced blast simulators, commonly used in pre-clinical TBI research, generate controlled, repeatable shock waves that allow researchers to isolate the effects of

overpressure on the brain ^{46,103,104}. These models provide a valuable tool for investigating fundamental injury mechanisms but may not fully replicate the complex characteristics of operational blast exposure, such as the prolonged negative phase, decay rate, complex wave reflections, and impulse from open field explosions. As a result, not all experimental blast configurations reproduce the features of operational blast exposure. Identifying which experimental waveforms represent incoming and outgoing military exposure remains a challenge for blast research.

Experimental Blast Configurations Used in Pre-Clinical Models

Pre-clinical blast researchers currently have three main options for controlled exposure. In this paper, unconfined, partially confined, and fully confined blast are defined based on experimental boundary conditions. While these experimental configurations are defined by laboratory boundary conditions, they are motivated by the need to approximate operational military blast exposures. Incoming and outgoing blast threats encountered by military personnel have a range of waveform characteristics that overlap with but are not fully captured by any single experimental configuration.

1. **Unconfined Exposures** – Unconfined blasts are explosive charges placed directly on the ground within an open test environment such that the detonation products are free to expand without interacting with nearby reflective surfaces ^{21,73}. In idealized conditions, these configurations produce a classic Friedlander waveform, characterized by a rapid pressure rise, a brief positive phase, and a gradual decay into a negative phase shown in Figure 3A. True unconfined conditions are rare in operational military settings. Incoming threats such as artillery or munitions typically detonate above the ground or near surrounding structures introducing reflections in the waveform.
2. **Partially Confined Exposures** – Partially confined blast exposures occur when an explosive charge is positioned at some distance above the ground or near structures that introduce reflective boundaries without fully enclosing the blast wave. In these configurations, interactions with the ground or structures generate reflected waves that increase the number of reflection peaks as seen in Figure 3B. Many operational blast exposures share characteristics with partially confined experimental configurations. Incoming threats such as near ground detonations and outgoing exposures from breaching charges and shoulder fired weapons systems produce waveforms with multiple reflections.
3. **Fully Confined Exposures** – Fully confined exposures occur in enclosed or sealed environments, such as shock tubes (gas or air driven), blast simulators (gas or air driven), or blast tubes (explosively driven). In these settings, the wave has little space for wave expansion, leading to an extended duration ^{27,60,71} seen in Figure 3C. Although these systems are fully confined, the shock loading is uniform and designed for a planar (flat) shock wave front. This uniformity distinguishes fully confined laboratory blasts from operational confined blast events such as enclosed vehicle detonations or tunnel blasts

where multiple reflections occur from non-uniform structures leading to multiple peaks in the pressure waveform.

Figure 3: Types of blasts and corresponding pressure vs time profiles A: Unconfined, B: Partially Confined C: Fully Confined¹⁰⁵

Challenges in Translating Pre-Clinical Models to Military TBI

Blast exposure studies encompass both small-scale controlled models and full-scale explosive tests, each with unique advantages and limitations. Full-scale blast tests, such as those assessing underbody blasts on military vehicles^{64,106,107}, provide data on musculoskeletal loading, spinal injuries, and overall vehicle survivability. These tests often study whole-body trauma but prioritize structural integrity and survivability over the detailed study of bTBI. This makes it difficult to isolate overpressure effects from blunt force trauma and acceleration-related injuries, which can be major contributors to brain injury in operational environments. Small-scale pre-clinical studies using explosives^{13,17}, shock tubes^{7,18} and blast simulators¹⁵ allow researchers to isolate pressure effects on the brain, making them valuable for controlled TBI research.

Review of Pre-Clinical Blast Models: What Do They Represent?

Pre-clinical models of blast exposure are essential for investigating the physiological and neurological effects of bTBI. However, substantial heterogeneity in experimental approaches contribute to variability in reported outcomes across studies. Models differ widely in the mechanisms used to generate blast waves, the magnitude and duration of exposure, and the anatomical regions subjected to loading. This review includes pre-clinical blast models classified according to the fundamental mechanism of overpressure generation, explosive-based, gas-driven, and wire-driven models, rather than by the specific device used, such as shock tubes or open-field

setups. Each category has distinct strengths and limitations, particularly with respect to fidelity in replicating real-world blast environments.

Explosive-Driven TBI Models

Explosively-driven models use detonations to generate high-pressure blast waves for studying brain injuries resulting from blast exposure. They have been applied in small and large-animal studies and are typically conducted in open-field environments or controlled blast tubes, where detonation-induced overpressure propagates through air before reaching the test subject^{12–14,17,108–111}. Explosive charges can range from small-scale detonations to larger military-grade explosives, with exposure intensities adjusted based on charge size, distance, and environmental conditions.

One of the key advantages of explosive-based models is their ability to produce realistic blast waveforms, including the coupled positive and negative phases, and decay rate congruent with free air expansion. These models can also be used to capture secondary effects such as heat, debris, and tertiary injuries from acceleration forces. Pre-clinical explosive models in rodents span a range of peak overpressures, from approximately 17 kPa to 46.6 kPa^{12,17,108,109,112–114}. This range overlaps with measured pressures from operational military weapons, providing context for the relevance of pre-clinical exposures. For example, shoulder-fired weapons produce peak pressures on the order of 48 kPa for a Carl Gustaf, 45 kPa for a SMAW, 24 kPa for an M72 LAW, and 27 kPa for an AT4CS³².

Gas-Driven TBI Models

Gas-driven models simulate blast exposure using compressed gas or controlled detonation of gas mixtures to generate shock waves. These setups often involve advanced blast simulators or shock tubes where rapid gas expansion creates high-pressure waves that propagate toward the test subject^{27,104,115–119}. Unlike explosive-based models, gas-driven methods allow for greater experimental control and do not require access to explosives or specialized permits, making them accessible to a wide range of research institutions.

Despite practical advantages, gas-based models have inherent limitations in replicating explosive blasts. Many laboratory blast simulators produce waveforms with little to no negative phase and pressure decay rate slower than that of an open air environment²⁷. Peak pressures reported in rodent studies range from 30 to 550 kPa^{7,120–125}, often exceeding those generated by outgoing threats (~24–48 kPa)³², making them more applicable to incoming threat analysis.

To assess how accurately laboratory blast simulators reproduce the characteristics of free-field blast waves, parameters reported in a recent multi-institutional study were examined¹²⁶. The study compared four blast simulators and found that, even when configured to produce comparable peak overpressures (69 and 103 kPa), substantial variability in positive phase duration persisted across sites. For the 69 kPa target, positive phase durations ranged from 3 to 6 ms, with an average around 4 ms. For the 103kPa condition durations ranged from 3 to 7 ms, averaging around 5 ms¹²⁶. Using these durations as reference points, an online Kingery–Bulmash calculator was employed to

estimate equivalent free-field explosive conditions¹²⁷. A charge mass of 0.5 kg TNT, representative of pre-clinical open field blasts tests reported in literature^{12,13,17,112,113,128-130}, was chosen to provide a realistic comparison to laboratory scale exposures. When matching the reported blast simulator positive phase durations of 4-5 ms, the corresponding free-field incident overpressures at 9-20 m from the charge were only 4.5-12 kPa, well below the reported blast simulator targets. Conversely when matching the blast simulator peak overpressures of 69 and 103 kPa, the equivalent free field durations at 2.5-3.1 m from the charge were 2.3-2.7 ms, shorter than those produced in the blast simulators.

Collectively, these comparisons suggest that shock tubes may have inherent limitations in simultaneously replicating both the peak overpressure and positive phase duration characteristic of open-air detonations. As a result, models relying solely on peak overpressure or duration may not fully capture the realistic impulse and waveform dynamics that drive biological responses in operational blast environments. Combining the parameters into a pressure duration ratio¹³¹ or impulse based metric may provide a more representative measure of the mechanical loading experienced by the brain and improve comparability across studies.

Wire-Based TBI Models

Wire-driven models represent an alternative approach to studying blast-induced TBI, focusing on intracranial mechanical loading rather than free field air blasts. These models use rapid wire vaporization in water to generate pressure waves, exposing tissue preparations or cultured cells to blast like conditions¹³²⁻¹³⁶. Advantages include precise control and repeatability, making them increasingly popular for in vitro studies, such as brain organoids, where low-pressure inputs in water can be amplified compared to air. As a result, pressures measured in water cannot be directly compared to air-blast pressures; they reflect energy transmitted to tissue rather than external blast characteristics. These models are not attempting to reproduce air-blast waveforms, reflections, or negative phases, and are therefore not direct battlefield analogs. Many wire driven models are designed to approximate the intracranial loading conditions that may arise when the head is exposed to air blast. Their value lies in isolating tissue-level responses and bridging the gap between cellular studies and whole-animal blast exposures, providing mechanistic insight into how energy is transmitted to the brain during blast events.

Conclusion

Blast-induced TBI remains a critical concern for both military personnel and the civilian population, underscoring the need for accurate and reproducible pre-clinical models to elucidate its underlying mechanisms and long-term outcomes. Despite substantial advances in experimental capability, considerable variability in model design, blast generation methods, and exposure parameters continue to limit translational relevance. This review categorized pre-clinical blast models based on the source of the event, whether representing incoming threats (open-field or operational blasts) or outgoing threats (weapon discharge) assessing their ability to replicate real-world military exposures. Across model types, many systems fail to capture key aspects of true

blast exposure, including the full temporal profile of overpressure, realistic impulse, duration, and negative phase dynamics.

Explosively-driven models offer the highest fidelity to true battlefield conditions and, when carefully controlled, can achieve repeatability in pressure history. However, they remain constrained by safety considerations and logistical complexity. In contrast, gas-driven systems, such as advanced blast simulators, provide enhanced control and repeatability yet may not fully reproduce realistic impulse, duration and negative phase dynamics. A clear understanding of these trade-offs is essential for selecting appropriate models and refining experimental paradigms to enhance translational value.

Recognizing that both pressure magnitude and duration contribute to injury risk, future studies should incorporate both metrics such as a pressure-duration ratio when characterizing blast conditions. Such parameters may provide a more physiologically meaningful link between mechanical loading and biological response. Equally important is clarifying the distinction between blast and shock exposures, as many laboratory blast systems generate shock waveforms that do not fully represent the coupled dynamics of explosive detonations and subsequent free-field overpressure expansion and decay. Future work should prioritize continued improvements in model realism, including the incorporation of wave reflection, repeated exposures, and negative phase effects similar to real life blast events. In parallel, broad adoption of blast relevant common data elements offers a practical pathway toward greater harmonization across laboratories by standardizing how exposure conditions are reported and compared. Moreover, the development of standardized exposure thresholds will strengthen cross-study comparability and translational relevance. By more closely aligning pre-clinical blast models with operational and battlefield conditions, future research can more effectively inform protective strategies, diagnostic approaches and therapeutic interventions for blast-related injuries.

Transparency, Rigor, and Reproducibility Statement

The review was not preregistered because it falls under the category of a traditional literature review that employed a systematic search strategy but did not implement full systematic review methodology or quantitative meta-analysis. A comprehensive literature search was conducted using PubMed, Web of Science, and Google Scholar to identify peer-reviewed studies describing pre-clinical blast models, including explosive-based, gas-driven, and wire-driven approaches. Search terms included combinations of “blast,” “TBI,” “shock tube,” “explosive model,” “gas-driven blast,” “overpressure,” and “pre-clinical.” Additional relevant publications were identified through reference chaining from review articles. As this review involved only publicly available literature and did not include individual patient data, institutional review board approval was not required.

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Author contribution (after acknowledgements)

R.L.B.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing—original draft, review and editing. P.J.V.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing review and editing. C.E.J.: Conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, supervision, writing review and editing

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Data availability

All data used throughout the manuscript is provided in the paper.

References

1. Belding JN, Englert R, Bonkowski J, et al. Occupational Risk of Low-Level Blast Exposure and TBI-Related Medical Diagnoses: A Population-Based Epidemiological Investigation (2005–2015). *Int J Environ Res Public Health* 2021; 18: 12925.
2. Blakey SM, Wagner HR, Naylor J, et al. Chronic Pain, TBI, and PTSD in Military Veterans: A Link to Suicidal Ideation and Violent Impulses? *J Pain* 2018; 19: 797–806.
3. Goodrich GL, Flyg HM, Kirby JE, et al. Mechanisms of TBI and Visual Consequences in Military and Veteran Populations. *Optom Vis Sci* 2013; 90: 105–112.

4. Gupta RK, Przekwas A. Mathematical Models of Blast-Induced TBI: Current Status, Challenges, and Prospects. *Front Neurol*; 4. Epub ahead of print 2013. DOI: 10.3389/fneur.2013.00059.
5. Jurick SM, Crocker LD, Merritt VC, et al. Independent and Synergistic Associations Between TBI Characteristics and PTSD Symptom Clusters on Cognitive Performance and Postconcussive Symptoms in Iraq and Afghanistan Veterans. *J Neuropsychiatry Clin Neurosci* 2021; 33: 98–108.
6. Fesharaki-Zadeh A, Datta D. An overview of preclinical models of traumatic brain injury (TBI): relevance to pathophysiological mechanisms. *Front Cell Neurosci*; 18. Epub ahead of print 12 April 2024. DOI: 10.3389/fncel.2024.1371213.
7. Mishra V, Skotak M, Schuetz H, et al. Primary blast causes mild, moderate, severe and lethal TBI with increasing blast overpressures: Experimental rat injury model. *Sci Rep* 2016; 6: 26992.
8. Needham CE, Ritzel D, Rule GT, et al. Blast Testing Issues and TBI: Experimental Models That Lead to Wrong Conclusions. *Front Neurol*; 6. Epub ahead of print 8 April 2015. DOI: 10.3389/fneur.2015.00072.
9. Hanna M, Pfister B. An approach for studying the direct effect of shock waves on neuronal cell structure and function. Epub ahead of print 3 October 2024. DOI: 10.21203/rs.3.rs-4908725/v1.
10. Kamnaksh A, Kwon S-K, Kovesdi E, et al. Neurobehavioral, cellular, and molecular consequences of single and multiple mild blast exposure: Proteomics and 2DE. *ELECTROPHORESIS* 2012; 33: 3680–3692.
11. Sajja VSSS, Perrine SA, Ghoddoussi F, et al. Blast neurotrauma impairs working memory and disrupts prefrontal myo-inositol levels in rats. *Mol Cell Neurosci* 2014; 59: 119–126.
12. Konan LM, Song H, Pentecost G, et al. Multi-Focal Neuronal Ultrastructural Abnormalities and Synaptic Alterations in Mice after Low-Intensity Blast Exposure. *J Neurotrauma* 2019; 36: 2117–2128.
13. Ma Y, Tang Q, Cheng X, et al. UTE MRI for Assessing Demyelination in an mTBI Mouse Model: An Open-field Low-intensity Blast Study. *NeuroImage* 2025; 121103.
14. Axelsson H, Hjelmqvist H, Medin A, et al. Physiological changes in pigs exposed to a blast wave from a detonating high-explosive charge. *Mil Med* 2000; 165: 119–126.
15. McNeil E, Walilko T, Hulbert LE, et al. Development of a Minipig Model of BINT From Blast Exposure Using a Repeatable Mobile Shock Expansion Tube. *Mil Med* 2023; 188: e591–e599.
16. Säljö A, Arrhén F, Bolouri H, et al. Neuropathology and pressure in the pig brain resulting from low-impulse noise exposure. *J Neurotrauma* 2008; 25: 1397–1406.

17. Chen M, Song H, Cui J, et al. Proteomic Profiling of Mouse Brains Exposed to Blast-Induced Mild Traumatic Brain Injury Reveals Changes in Axonal Proteins and Phosphorylated Tau. *J Alzheimers Dis* 2018; 66: 751–773.
18. Alay E, Skotak M, Misistia A, et al. Dynamic loads on human and animal surrogates at different test locations in compressed-gas-driven shock tubes. *Shock Waves* 2018; 28: 51–62.
19. Chandra N, Sundaramurthy A, Gupta RK. Validation of Laboratory Animal and Surrogate Human Models in Primary Blast Injury Studies. *Mil Med* 2017; 182: 105–113.
20. Liang J, Smith KD, Gan RZ, et al. The effect of blast overpressure on the mechanical properties of the human tympanic membrane. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater* 2019; 100: 103368.
21. Langenderfer M, Williams K, Douglas A, et al. An evaluation of measured and predicted air blast parameters from partially confined blast waves. *Shock Waves* 2021; 31: 175–192.
22. Cooper PW. *Explosives engineering*. New York, N.Y.: VCH, 1996.
23. Chandra N, Ganpule S, Kleinschmit NN, et al. Evolution of blast wave profiles in simulated air blasts: experiment and computational modeling. *Shock Waves* 2012; 22: 403–415.
24. Sundaramurthy A, Chandra N. A Parametric Approach to Shape Field-Relevant Blast Wave Profiles in Compressed-Gas-Driven Shock Tube. *Front Neurol*; 5, <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fneur.2014.00253> (2014, accessed 24 January 2023).
25. Hampton CE, Thorpe CN, Sholar CA, et al. A novel bridge wire model of blast traumatic brain injury - biomed 2013. *Biomed Sci Instrum* 2013; 49: 312–319.
26. Hernández Garcia F, Rojas Mata S, Apazidis N, et al. Characterization of underwater blast waves from Cu wire explosions using high-resolution pressure measurements. *Phys Fluids* 2025; 37: 086115.
27. Bauer RL, Johnson CE. Blast tube design: How shape and size influence the resultant shock wave. *AIP Adv* 2025; 15: 025030.
28. Bauer RL, Johnson EM, Douglas AD, et al. Effect of shock tunnel geometry on shockwave and vortex ring formation, propagation, and head on collision. *Phys Fluids* 2023; 35: 085136.
29. Kamimori GH, Reilly LA, LaValle CR, et al. Occupational overpressure exposure of breachers and military personnel. *Shock Waves* 2017; 27: 837–847.
30. Walilko TJ. Effects of Common Breaching Practices on the Overpressures Recorded Within the Stack. American Society of Mechanical Engineers Digital Collection. Epub ahead of print 13 March 2015. DOI: 10.1115/IMECE2014-38399.

31. Tate CM, Wang KKW, Eonta S, et al. Serum Brain Biomarker Level, Neurocognitive Performance, and Self-Reported Symptom Changes in Soldiers Repeatedly Exposed to Low-Level Blast: A Breacher Pilot Study. *J Neurotrauma* 2013; 30: 1620–1630.
32. Wiri S, Massow T, Reid J, et al. Dynamic monitoring of service members to quantify blast exposure levels during combat training using BlackBox Biometrics Blast Gauges: explosive breaching, shoulder-fired weapons, artillery, mortars, and 0.50 caliber guns. *Front Neurol*; 14. Epub ahead of print 25 May 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fneur.2023.1175671>.
33. Wiri S, Ritter AC, Bailie JM, et al. Computational Modeling of blast exposure associated with recoilless weapons combat training. *Shock Waves* 2017; 27: 849–862.
34. Medda A, Carr W, Funk R, et al. Infrasound signature measurements for U.S. Army infantry weapons during training. *J Acoust Soc Am* 2021; 150: A214–A215.
35. Bochorishvili N, Akhvlediani I, Chikhradze N, et al. Study of the Impact of Mine Blast on Armored Vehicle Occupants by the Physical Modelling. *IOP Conf Ser Earth Environ Sci* 2019; 221: 012107.
36. Loftis KL, Mazuchowski EL II, Clouser MC, et al. Prominent Injury Types in Vehicle Underbody Blast. *Mil Med* 2019; 184: 261–264.
37. Wiri S, Needham CE. Reconstruction of improvised explosive device blast loading to personnel in the open. *Shock Waves*. DOI: 10.1007/s00193-016-0644-1.
38. Kamimori GH, McQuiggan W, Ramos AN, et al. An Exploratory Comparison of Water-Tamped and -Untamped Explosive Breaches: Practical Applications for the Tactical Community via a Pilot Study. *J Spec Oper Med Peer Rev J SOF Med Prof* 2022; 22: 56–59.
39. Wiri S, Needham C. Quantifying Blast Exposure Levels on Humans. In: *Proceedings of the 32nd International Symposium on Shock Waves (ISSW32 2019)*. Research Publishing Services, pp. 1097–1107.
40. Bailie JM, Lipka SM, Hungerford L, et al. Cumulative Blast Exposure During a Military Career Negatively Impacts Recovery from Traumatic Brain Injury. *J Neurotrauma* 2024; 41: 604–612.
41. Lieb DA, Raiciulescu S, DeGraba T, et al. Investigation of the Relationship Between Frequency of Blast Exposure, mTBI History, and Post-traumatic Stress Symptoms. *Mil Med* 2022; 187: e702–e710.
42. Epshtein E, Shraga S, Radomislensky I, et al. Blast Injury and Chronic Psychiatric Disability in Military Personnel: Exploring the Association Beyond Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. *J Psychiatr Res*. Epub ahead of print 19 March 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.jpsychires.2025.03.026.
43. Gilmore N, Tseng C-EJ, Maffei C, et al. Impact of repeated blast exposure on active-duty United States Special Operations Forces. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2024; 121: e2313568121.

44. McEvoy C, Crabtree A, Case J, et al. Cumulative Blast Impulse Is Predictive for Changes in Chronic Neurobehavioral Symptoms Following Low Level Blast Exposure during Military Training. *Mil Med* 2024; 189: e2069–e2077.
45. Rowland JA, Martindale SL. Considerations for the assessment of blast exposure in service members and veterans. *Front Neurol*; 15. Epub ahead of print 15 April 2024. DOI: 10.3389/fneur.2024.1383710.
46. Arun P, Wilder DM, Eken O, et al. Long-Term Effects of Blast Exposure: A Functional Study in Rats Using an Advanced Blast Simulator. *J Neurotrauma* 2020; 37: 647–655.
47. Eastridge BJ, Mabry RL, Seguin P, et al. Death on the battlefield (2001–2011): Implications for the future of combat casualty care. *J Trauma Acute Care Surg* 2012; 73: S431.
48. Belding JN, Egnoto M, Englert RM, et al. Getting on the Same Page: Consolidating Terminology to Facilitate Cross-Disciplinary Health-Related Blast Research. *Front Neurol* 2021; 12: 695496.
49. Sharma M, Singh H, Gupta A, et al. Target identification and control model of autopilot for passive homing missiles | Multimedia Tools and Applications. 83. Epub ahead of print 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-17804-6>.
50. Benesch B. The JLTV Applies Lessons Learned in Underbody Blast Protection. *DSIAC*; 4, <https://dsiac.dtic.mil/articles/the-jltv-applies-lessons-learned-in-underbody-blast-protection/> (2017, accessed 4 November 2025).
51. Vartanian O, Tenn C, Rhind SG, et al. Blast in Context: The Neuropsychological and Neurocognitive Effects of Long-Term Occupational Exposure to Repeated Low-Level Explosives on Canadian Armed Forces' Breaching Instructors and Range Staff. *Front Neurol*; 11. Epub ahead of print 3 December 2020. DOI: 10.3389/fneur.2020.588531.
52. Reid MW, Miller KJ, Lange RT, et al. A Multisite Study of the Relationships between Blast Exposures and Symptom Reporting in a Post-Deployment Active Duty Military Population with Mild Traumatic Brain Injury. *J Neurotrauma* 2014; 31: 1899–1906.
53. Shreve BP. The Modern Explosive Threat: Improvised Explosive Devices. In: Callaway DW, Burstein JL (eds) *Operational and Medical Management of Explosive and Blast Incidents*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 99–107.
54. Ling G, Ecklund JM, Bandak FA. Chapter 11 - Brain injury from explosive blast: description and clinical management. In: Grafman J, Salazar AM (eds) *Handbook of Clinical Neurology*. Elsevier, pp. 173–180.
55. Department of Kinesiology, The University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX 76019, USA, Wilson JR. Blast-Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) with Post-traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD): A Treatable Condition? *Psychol Cogn Sci – Open J* 2017; 3: e19–e22.

56. Magnuson J, Ling G, Magnuson J, et al. Explosive Blast Mild Traumatic Brain Injury. In: *Traumatic Brain Injury - Pathobiology, Advanced Diagnostics and Acute Management*. IntechOpen. Epub ahead of print 9 May 2018. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.74035.
57. Anthistle T, Fletcher DI, Tyas A. Characterisation of blast loading in complex, confined geometries using quarter symmetry experimental methods. *Shock Waves* 2016; 26: 749–757.
58. Sochet I, Gardebas D, Calderara S, et al. Blast Wave Parameters for Spherical Explosives Detonation in Free Air. *Open J Saf Sci Technol* 2011; 01: 31–42.
59. Sochet I, Gault K, Hakenholz L, et al. Propagation of Shock Waves in Two Rooms Communicating through an Opening. In: *Direct Numerical Simulations - An Introduction and Applications*. IntechOpen. Epub ahead of print 27 June 2019. DOI: 10.5772/intechopen.87190.
60. Sochet I, Sauvan P-E, Trelat S. Analysis of reflected blast wave pressure profiles in a confined room. *Shock Waves* 2012; 22: 253–264.
61. Bazhenova TV, Gvozdeva LG, Zhilin YuV. Change in the shape of the diffracting shock wave at a convex corner. *Acta Astronaut* 1979; 6: 401–412.
62. Ahlers S, Vasserman-Stokes E, Shaughness M, et al. Assessment of the Effects of Acute and Repeated Exposure to Blast Overpressure in Rodents: Toward a Greater Understanding of Blast and the Potential Ramifications for Injury in Humans Exposed to Blast. *Front Neurol*; 3, <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fneur.2012.00032> (2012, accessed 17 November 2023).
63. Edlow BL, Bodien YG, Baxter T, et al. Long-Term Effects of Repeated Blast Exposure in United States Special Operations Forces Personnel: A Pilot Study Protocol. *J Neurotrauma* 2022; 39: 1391–1407.
64. Babu V, Thyagarajan R, Ramalingam J. Faster Method of Simulating Military Vehicles Exposed to Fragmenting Underbody IED Threats. pp. 2017-01–0264.
65. Juan A. Shoulder-fired weapons can cause traumatic brain injuries, study finds. *Louisiana Department of Veterans Affairs*, <https://www.vetaffairs.la.gov/shoulder-fired-weapons-can-cause-traumatic-brain-injuries-study-finds/> (2018, accessed 29 September 2023).
66. Blast exposure from firing heavy weapons potentially causing unrecognized brain injuries. *Concussion Alliance*, <https://www.concussionalliance.org/blog/blast-exposure-from-firing-heavy-weapons-potentially-causing-unrecognized-brain-injuries> (accessed 25 March 2025).
67. Carr W, Stone JR, Walilko T, et al. Repeated Low-Level Blast Exposure: A Descriptive Human Subjects Study. *Mil Med* 2016; 181: 28–39.
68. Medda A, Funk R, Ahuja K, et al. Measurements of Infrasound Signatures From Grenade Blast During Training. *Mil Med* 2021; 186: 523–528.

69. Remennikov A, Mentus I, Uy B. Explosive Breaching of Walls with Contact Charges: Theory and Applications. *Int J Prot Struct* 2015; 6: 629–648.
70. Loflin AR, Johnson CE. A review of current safe distance calculations and the risk of mild traumatic brain injury. *Shock Waves* 2024; 34: 303–314.
71. Rezaei A, Salimi Jazi M, Javid S, et al. Confined blasts, and the impact of shock wave reflections on a human head and the related traumatic brain injury. *Int J Exp Comput Biomech* 2014; 2: 205–222.
72. Blair DP. Charge Weight Scaling Laws and the Superposition of Blast Vibration Waves. *Fragblast* 2004; 8: 221–239.
73. Johnson EM, Grahl N, Langenderfer MJ, et al. An experimental and simulated investigation into the validity of unrestricted blast wave scaling models when applied to transonic flow in complex tunnel environments. *Int J Prot Struct* 2022; 20414196221095252.
74. Jean A, Nyein MK, Zheng JQ, et al. An animal-to-human scaling law for blast-induced traumatic brain injury risk assessment. *Proc Natl Acad Sci* 2014; 111: 15310–15315.
75. Panzer MB, Wood GW, Bass CR. Scaling in neurotrauma: how do we apply animal experiments to people? *Exp Neurol* 2014; 261: 120–126.
76. Zhu F, Chou CC, Yang KH, et al. Some considerations on the threshold and inter-species scaling law for primary blast-induced traumatic brain injury: a semi-analytical approach. *J Mech Med Biol* 2013; 13: 1350065.
77. Chandra N, Ganpule S, Kleinschmit NN, et al. Evolution of blast wave profiles in simulated air blasts: experiment and computational modeling. *Shock Waves* 2012; 22: 403–415.
78. Courant R, Friedrichs KO. *Supersonic Flow and Shock Waves*. Springer Science & Business Media, 1999.
79. Davis WC. Shock Waves; Rarefaction Waves; Equations of State. In: Zukas JA, Walters WP (eds) *Explosive Effects and Applications*. New York, NY: Springer, pp. 47–113.
80. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. Speed of Sound. grc.nasa.gov, <https://www.grc.nasa.gov/www/k-12/BGP/sound.html> (2021, accessed 28 March 2025).
81. Dewey JM. Measurement of the Physical Properties of Blast Waves. In: Igra O, Seiler F (eds) *Experimental Methods of Shock Wave Research*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 53–86.
82. Cooper PW. Introduction to Detonation Physics. In: Zukas JA, Walters WP (eds) *Explosive Effects and Applications*. New York, NY: Springer, pp. 115–135.

83. Andrews SA. Verification and validation of detonation-shock-dynamics relations for explosives described by general equation of state and chemical reaction models. *Combust Theory Model* 2024; 0: 1–25.
84. Bdzil JB. Steady-state two-dimensional detonation. *J Fluid Mech* 1981; 108: 195–226.
85. Bdzil JB, Stewart DS. Theory of Detonation Shock Dynamics. In: Zhang F (ed) *Shock Waves Science and Technology Library, Vol. 6: Detonation Dynamics*. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, pp. 373–453.
86. Bdzil JB, Stewart DS. The Dynamics of Detonation in Explosive Systems. *Annu Rev Fluid Mech* 2007; 39: 263–292.
87. Boutillier J, Ehrhardt L, De Mezzo S, et al. Evaluation of the existing triple point path models with new experimental data: proposal of an original empirical formulation. *Shock Waves* 2018; 28: 243–252.
88. Guerke GH, Scheklinski-Glueck G. *Blast Parameters from Cylindrical Charges Detonated on the Surface of the Ground*. ADP000430, Freiburg, Germany.
89. Choubey B, Dutta SC, Prakhya GKV, et al. Blast pressure analysis due to confined explosion-after effects. *Structures* 2020; 28: 521–536.
90. Shin J, Whittaker AS, Cormie D. Incident and Normally Reflected Overpressure and Impulse for Detonations of Spherical High Explosives in Free Air. *J Struct Eng* 2015; 141: 04015057.
91. Yang B, Cao Z, Chang Z, et al. The effect of the reflected shock wave on the foam material. *Int J Impact Eng* 2021; 149: 103773.
92. Hosseini H, Moosavi-Nejad S, Akiyama H, et al. Shock wave interaction with interfaces between materials having different acoustic impedances. *Appl Phys Lett* 2014; 104: 103701.
93. Musa AB. The effective ratio of acoustic impedance in predicting stress and velocity of wave propagation in viscoelastic material (standard linear solid model). Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, pp. 146–151.
94. Fievisohn E, Bailey Z, Guettler A, et al. Primary Blast Brain Injury Mechanisms: Current Knowledge, Limitations, and Future Directions. *J Biomech Eng*; 140. Epub ahead of print 1 February 2018. DOI: 10.1115/1.4038710.
95. Alves-Pereira M, Castelo Branco NAA. Vibroacoustic disease: Biological effects of infrasound and low-frequency noise explained by mechanotransduction cellular signalling. *Prog Biophys Mol Biol* 2007; 93: 256–279.
96. Araújo Alves J, Neto Paiva F, Torres Silva L, et al. Low-Frequency Noise and Its Main Effects on Human Health—A Review of the Literature between 2016 and 2019. *Appl Sci* 2020; 10: 5205.

97. Chaban R, Ghazy A, Georgiade E, et al. Negative Effect of High-Level Infrasound on Human Myocardial Contractility: In-Vitro Controlled Experiment. *Noise Health* 2021; 23: 57–66.
98. Elmenhorst E-M, Elmenhorst D, Wenzel J, et al. Effects of nocturnal aircraft noise on cognitive performance in the following morning: dose-response relationships in laboratory and field. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* 2010; 83: 743–751.
99. Hikishima K, Tsurugizawa T, Kasahara K, et al. Functional ultrasound reveals effects of MRI acoustic noise on brain function. *NeuroImage* 2023; 281: 120382.
100. Jafari MJ, Khosrowabadi R, Khodakarim S, et al. The Effect of Noise Exposure on Cognitive Performance and Brain Activity Patterns. *Open Access Maced J Med Sci* 2019; 7: 2924–2931.
101. Grogan SP, Mount CA. Ultrasound Physics and Instrumentation. In: *StatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing, <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK570593/> (2025, accessed 28 March 2025).
102. Ash C, Dubec M, Donne K, et al. Effect of wavelength and beam width on penetration in light-tissue interaction using computational methods. *Lasers Med Sci* 2017; 32: 1909–1918.
103. Gan ECJ, Remennikov A, Ritzel D, et al. Approximating a far-field blast environment in an advanced blast simulator for explosion resistance testing. *Int J Prot Struct* 2020; 11: 468–493.
104. Nelson AJ, Ritzel D, Showalter N, et al. Characterization of an Advanced Blast Simulator for Investigation of Large Scale Blast Traumatic Brain Injury Studies. *Ann Biomed Eng*. Epub ahead of print 14 September 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s10439-024-03618-6.
105. Facilities and Equipment, https://tntlab.beam.vt.edu/content/tntlab_beam_vt_edu/en/LabFacilities.html (accessed 7 January 2026).
106. Ashworth E, Baxter D, Gibb I, et al. Injuries in Underbody Blast Fatalities: Identification of Five Distinct Mechanisms of Head Injury. *J Neurotrauma* 2023; 40: 141–147.
107. Lei J, Zhu F, Jiang B, et al. Underbody blast effect on the pelvis and lumbar spine: A computational study. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater* 2018; 79: 9–19.
108. Rubovitch V, Ten-Bosch M, Zohar O, et al. A mouse model of blast-induced mild traumatic brain injury. *Exp Neurol* 2011; 232: 280–289.
109. Tweedie D, Rachmany L, Rubovitch V, et al. Changes in mouse cognition and hippocampal gene expression observed in a mild physical- and blast-traumatic brain injury. *Neurobiol Dis* 2013; 54: 1–11.

110. Kallakuri S, Desai A, Feng K, et al. Neuronal Injury and Glial Changes Are Hallmarks of Open Field Blast Exposure in Swine Frontal Lobe. *PLoS ONE* 2017; 12: e0169239.
111. Feng K, Zhang L, Jin X, et al. Biomechanical Responses of the Brain in Swine Subject to Free-Field Blasts. *Front Neurol*; 7. Epub ahead of print 24 October 2016. DOI: 10.3389/fneur.2016.00179.
112. Jackson M, Chen S, Liu P, et al. Quantitative proteomic profiling in brain subregions of mice exposed to open-field low-intensity blast reveals position-dependent blast effects. *Shock Waves*. Epub ahead of print 25 April 2024. DOI: 10.1007/s00193-024-01169-2.
113. Song H, Chen M, Chen C, et al. Proteomic Analysis and Biochemical Correlates of Mitochondrial Dysfunction after Low-Intensity Primary Blast Exposure. *J Neurotrauma* 2019; 36: 1591–1605.
114. Song H, Konan LM, Cui J, et al. Ultrastructural brain abnormalities and associated behavioral changes in mice after low-intensity blast exposure. *Behav Brain Res* 2018; 347: 148–157.
115. Baalman KL, Cotton RJ, Rasband SN, et al. Blast Wave Exposure Impairs Memory and Decreases Axon Initial Segment Length. *J Neurotrauma* 2013; 30: 741–751.
116. VandeVord PJ, Bolander R, Sajja VSSS, et al. Mild Neurotrauma Indicates a Range-Specific Pressure Response to Low Level Shock Wave Exposure. *Ann Biomed Eng* 2012; 40: 227–236.
117. Ning Y-L, Yang N, Chen X, et al. Chronic caffeine exposure attenuates blast-induced memory deficit in mice. *Chin J Traumatol* 2015; 18: 204–211.
118. Gullotti DM, Beamer M, Panzer MB, et al. Significant Head Accelerations Can Influence Immediate Neurological Impairments in a Murine Model of Blast-Induced Traumatic Brain Injury. *J Biomech Eng* 2014; 136: 091004.
119. Goldstein LE, Fisher AM, Tagge CA, et al. Chronic traumatic encephalopathy in blast-exposed military veterans and a blast neurotrauma mouse model. *Sci Transl Med* 2012; 4: 134ra60.
120. Awwad HO, Gonzalez LP, Tompkins P, et al. Blast Overpressure Waves Induce Transient Anxiety and Regional Changes in Cerebral Glucose Metabolism and Delayed Hyperarousal in Rats. *Front Neurol*; 6, <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fneur.2015.00132> (2015, accessed 17 November 2023).
121. Tompkins P, Tesiram Y, Lerner M, et al. Brain injury: neuro-inflammation, cognitive deficit, and magnetic resonance imaging in a model of blast induced traumatic brain injury. *J Neurotrauma* 2013; 30: 1888–1897.

122. Säljö A, Bolouri H, Mayorga M, et al. Low-level blast raises intracranial pressure and impairs cognitive function in rats: prophylaxis with processed cereal feed. *J Neurotrauma* 2010; 27: 383–389.
123. Cho HJ, Sajja VSSS, Vandevord PJ, et al. Blast induces oxidative stress, inflammation, neuronal loss and subsequent short-term memory impairment in rats. *Neuroscience* 2013; 253: 9–20.
124. Stemper BD, Shah AS, Budde MD, et al. Behavioral Outcomes Differ between Rotational Acceleration and Blast Mechanisms of Mild Traumatic Brain Injury. *Front Neurol* 2016; 7: 31.
125. Ibolja Cernak ZW Jianxin Jiang, Xiuwu Bian, Jovan Savic, null. Cognitive deficits following blast injury-induced neurotrauma: possible involvement of nitric oxide. *Brain Inj* 2001; 15: 593–612.
126. Lurski A, Clark J, Holt G, et al. Comparing Laboratory Blast Simulators and Exploring Influence on Helmet Test and Evaluation. In: *proceedings.com*. Bruges, Belgium: Royal Military Academy. Epub ahead of print 22 September 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.52202/081621-0035>.
127. Kingery-Bulmash Blast Parameter Calculator | International Ammunition Technical Guidelines, <https://unsafeguard.org/un-safeguard/kingery-bulmash> (accessed 29 August 2023).
128. Song H, Cui J, Simonyi A, et al. Linking blast physics to biological outcomes in mild traumatic brain injury: Narrative review and preliminary report of an open-field blast model. *Behav Brain Res* 2018; 340: 147–158.
129. Song H, Konan LM, Cui J, et al. Nanometer ultrastructural brain damage following low intensity primary blast wave exposure. *Neural Regen Res* 2018; 13: 1516–1519.
130. Kumar R, Sinha NR, Gupta S, et al. Open-Field Blast Injury Disrupts Corneal Gene Expression Linked to Ion Transport, Sensory Perception, and Neural Signaling. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci* 2025; 66: 68.
131. Rutter B, Song H, DePalma RG, et al. Shock Wave Physics as Related to Primary Non-Impact Blast-Induced Traumatic Brain Injury. *Mil Med* 2021; 186: 601–609.
132. Silvosa MJ, Mercado NR, Merlock N, et al. Understanding Primary Blast Injury: High Frequency Pressure Acutely Disrupts Neuronal Network Dynamics in Cerebral Organoids. *J Neurotrauma* 2022; 39: 1575–1590.
133. LaPlaca MC, Brody DL. Learning About Blast Injuries from Brain Organoids: A New Frontier. *J Neurotrauma* 2022; 39: 1453–1454.
134. Bar-Kochba E, Carneal CM, Alphonse VD, et al. Advancing next-generation brain organoid platforms for investigating traumatic brain injury from repeated blast exposures. *Front*

Bioeng Biotechnol; 13. Epub ahead of print 18 June 2025. DOI: 10.3389/fbioe.2025.1553609.

135. Hlavac N, Miller S, Grinter M, et al. Two and Three-Dimensional in Vitro Models of Blast-Induced Neurotrauma. *Biomed Sci Instrum* 2015; 51: 439–445.
136. Hlavac N, VandeVord PJ. Astrocyte Mechano-Activation by High-Rate Overpressure Involves Alterations in Structural and Junctional Proteins. *Front Neurol* 2019; 10: 99.